

MOVEMENT BEYOND EQUIPMENT: A RESOURCEFUL APPROACH IN TEACHING PHYSICAL EDUCATION IN CHALLENGING ENVIRONMENT

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed to determine the challenges encountered and strategies employed in teaching Physical Education in a challenging environment, particularly in small schools with limited facilities and resources. A quantitative descriptive research design was utilized, involving 30 Physical Education teachers from small secondary public schools in Sariaya and Candelaria, Quezon. The respondents were selected through a stratified random sampling technique. Data were gathered using a self-made questionnaire which explored the challenges as well as strategies in terms of Lesson Delivery, Student Engagement Technique, Assessment and Feedback, and Classroom Management. The data were analyzed using Weighted Arithmetic Mean to determine the most significant challenges and the least commonly applied strategies. In terms of challenges, results showed the following weighted means such as Lesson Delivery (3.70), Student Engagement Technique (3.67), Assessment and Feedback (3.64), and Classroom Management (3.70). On the other hand, for innovative teaching strategies, the weighted means for each variable were: Lesson Delivery (3.74), Student Engagement Technique (3.72), Assessment and Feedback (3.74), and Classroom Management (3.74). As shown in the result, the most challenging is the lesson delivery and classroom management while the least employed strategy is the student engagement technique. As an output, the researchers proposed a Program Plan which was designed to provide Physical Education teachers in resource-limited schools with structured, practical, and innovative strategies for effective lesson delivery, student engagement, assessment, and classroom management despite environmental challenges.

Keywords: *Physical Education, teaching challenges, limited facilities, innovative strategies*

INTRODUCTION

Physical education (PE) plays a vital role in fostering the overall development of students. It contributes not only to physical health but also to essential life skills such as discipline, teamwork, and stress management, all of which are crucial for academic success. However, despite its importance, many students experience limited access to quality physical education. Insufficient participation in regular physical activity has been associated with decreased concentration, lower energy levels, and difficulty coping with stress, which may negatively affect students' academic performance and study habits (Donnelly et al., 2016; Biddle et al., 2019; Centers for Disease Control and Prevention [CDC], 2022).

Globally, some countries have successfully integrated comprehensive PE programs. For instance, Finland, known for its high-quality facilities and highly trained PE teachers, consistently ranks among the top in academic performance. This success is partly attributed to the country's strong emphasis on physical education, which enhances both the health and academic outcomes of its schoolchildren (Johnson, 2022).

In recognition of the importance of physical activity, the Philippine Department of Education (DepEd) has integrated PE into the K to 12 Curriculum. This curriculum emphasizes fitness, movement education, and health-related fitness (HRF), aiming to develop lifelong healthy habits in students (DepEd, K to 12 Curriculum Guide Physical Education, 2016). Moreover, infrastructure projects such as the Basic Education Facilities Fund (BEFF) have been launched to improve school facilities, including gymnasium construction. However, despite these efforts, challenges remain in effectively implementing PE across various teaching environments in the Philippines.

There is a noticeable gap between the ideal goals of physical education and the current status of its implementation in many local schools. While some institutions have access to proper facilities and trained educators, others continue to struggle with limited resources and inconsistent program delivery. If this gap persists, it may hinder the potential of PE to contribute meaningfully to the holistic development of students.

Thus, this study aimed to explore the existing challenges and strategies employed in the implementation of physical education in small public secondary schools. By identifying these problems, the study sought to offer insights and recommendations that could help bridge the gap between policy intentions and on-ground realities. Ultimately, this research was essential in supporting efforts to enhance the quality and accessibility of physical education, particularly in under-resourced settings, and to inform future improvements in educational planning and delivery.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the challenges encountered and strategies employed in teaching Physical education in a challenging environment.

Specifically, it sought to answer the following research questions:

1. What are the challenges encountered by the respondents due to insufficient facilities in teaching physical education in terms of:
 - 1.1. Lesson Delivery;
 - 1.2. Student Engagement Technique;
 - 1.3. Assessment and Feedback; and
 - 1.4. Classroom Management?
2. What innovative teaching strategies are employed by the respondents in their physical education classes in terms of:
 - 2.1. Lesson Delivery;
 - 2.2. Student Engagement Technique;
 - 2.3. Assessment and Feedback; and
 - 2.4. Classroom Management?
3. Based on the research findings, what physical education classroom program plan can be proposed by the researchers?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study used a descriptive research design with a quantitative approach to determine the challenges encountered and strategies employed in teaching physical education in a challenging environment. According to Sirisilla (2023), descriptive research gathered detailed information about specific groups or phenomena without establishing cause-and-effect relationships. This method identified patterns and trends through surveys, observation, and case studies. The study examined how effective resourceful teaching strategies were in physical education, particularly in overcoming challenges posed by limited facilities and equipment. With this, the researchers utilized the descriptive method in this study since it aimed to determine the resourceful approach in teaching physical education in a challenging environment.

Research Locale

The study was conducted at five public secondary schools. Four were located in Sariaya and one in Candelaria, Quezon. These schools were selected as the research locale due to their commitment to providing quality Physical Education (PE) instruction despite being small and newly established, which often resulted in limited facilities and equipment. The study focused on physical education teachers in these institutions, as they played a vital role in implementing resourceful teaching strategies to enhance

student engagement and learning outcomes. Their experiences and insights provided valuable information on the effectiveness of innovative instructional approaches in overcoming barriers to PE instruction.

Furthermore, there was a need to examine how PE teachers adapted to teaching environments with resource constraints. While various strategies were employed, their impact on student participation, skill development, and overall instructional quality required further investigation. Given this, the study aimed to determine the resourceful approach and teaching strategies in ensuring quality PE instruction within challenging environments.

Research Population and Sample

The respondents of this study were Physical Education (PE) teachers employed from the different chosen locales during the academic year 2024 – 2025. These schools were selected due to their role in delivering Physical Education instruction within resource-limited environments, making them ideal for assessing the effectiveness of resourceful teaching strategies. To maintain an unbiased representation of the respondents, the researchers utilized a stratified random sampling technique. According to Hassan (2024), the stratified random sampling technique is used to obtain a representative sample from a population divided into relatively similar subpopulations (strata), ensuring that specific subgroups are adequately represented. This sampling approach ensured a systematic selection of participants, leading to a more comprehensive and organized process. From the total population, the final sample size became thirty (30) PE teachers proportionally distributed between the five schools and across teaching levels. The total population of the respondents was distributed as follows: five teachers from School A, four from School B, five from School C, eight from School D, and eight teachers from School E. To ensure fair representation, the study employed a stratified sampling technique, dividing respondents into subgroups based on their teaching level (junior or senior high school).

Research Instrument

The researchers used a self-made survey checklist questionnaire to determine the resourceful approach in teaching Physical Education in a challenging environment. The questionnaire consisted of two parts. The first part presented the challenges encountered by the respondents due to insufficient facilities in teaching physical education. The second part focused on the innovative teaching strategies employed by the respondents in their physical education classes in terms of Lesson Delivery, Student Engagement Technique, Assessment and Feedback, and Classroom Management. The questionnaire consists of 10 statements per variable, in a total of 80.

The researchers utilized a Likert scale to guide the respondents in rating the statements: 4 if the respondents Strongly Agreed (SA), 3 if they Agreed (A), 2 if they Disagreed (D), and 1 if they Strongly Disagreed (SD).

The questionnaire that was used in this study underwent a validation process to ensure accuracy and effectiveness. The content of the research instrument was validated by two experts in the Physical Education subject to ensure its relevance to the study. Also, the statements were validated by an English teacher for grammar.

Data Gathering Procedures

The data collection process for this study followed a structured approach to ensure the accuracy and reliability of the data gathered. First, the researchers sought formal approval from the principals of the chosen locale by submitting a letter of request outlining the purpose, objectives, and significance of the study. The letter also specified the involvement of Physical Education (PE) instructors as respondents. Upon receiving approval, the researchers coordinated with the designated school representatives to facilitate the smooth administration of the research instrument. Following the approval, the researchers personally administered the questionnaires to the Physical Education teachers from the selected schools. Prior to distribution, the researchers explained the purpose of the study and provided instructions on how to answer the survey. The respondents were given ample time to complete the questionnaire, ensuring they could provide thoughtful and accurate responses. The researchers also explained that the identity of the respondents will remain confidential for ethical reasons. Once the responses were collected, the researchers organized, tallied, and encoded the data for statistical analysis. The results derived from this process served as the foundation for the conclusions and recommendations of the study.

Statistical Treatment of Data

The researchers used the Weighted Arithmetic Mean (WAM) to analyze the data gathered about the challenges encountered by the respondents due to limited PE facilities and their innovative teaching strategies employed. The formula is as follows:

$$W = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n w_i X_i}{\sum_{i=1}^n w_i}$$

Where:

- W = Weighted Average
- n = Numbers of Terms to be Average
- W_i = Corresponding Weight
- X_i = Value of any particular

The researchers used a 4-Point Likert scale and interpreted the result using the continuous scale below.

Point Scale	Mean Range	Verbal Interpretation
4	3.26 - 4.00	Strongly Agree
3	2.51 - 3.25	Agree
2	1.76 - 2.50	Disagree
1	1.00 - 1.75	Strongly Disagree

RESULTS

This chapter presents the results of the study on the challenges and innovative teaching strategies experienced in teaching Physical Education due to insufficient facilities. The findings are discussed based on the sequence of the statement of the problems, presented in tables with supporting interpretations and literature.

Part I. Challenges Encountered due to Insufficient Facilities in Teaching Physical Education

Table 1

Challenges Encountered by the respondents due to Insufficient Facilities in Teaching Physical Education in terms of Lesson Delivery

No.	Statements	WAM	Verbal Description
1	Limited access to equipment affects the quality of PE instruction.	3.87	Strongly Agree
2	The lack of adequate space hinders effective lesson delivery.	3.83	Strongly Agree
5	The absence of specialized PE areas (e.g., gym, track) restricts activity options.	3.80	Strongly Agree
3	Inadequate teaching materials limit the use of diverse instructional methods.	3.73	Strongly Agree
4	Poor facility conditions affect students' learning motivation.	3.73	Strongly Agree
8	The lack of storage for equipment results in disorganized lesson delivery.	3.67	Strongly Agree
10	Due to limited classroom, classes are oversize and is hindered to effective individualized instruction.	3.63	Strongly Agree
7	Outdoor classes are often affected by weather conditions due to lack of covered spaces.	3.60	Strongly Agree

9	Limited availability of multimedia resources reduces the effectiveness of diverse instructional approaches.	3.57	Strongly Agree
6	Limited access to technology reduces the effectiveness of modern teaching strategies.	3.57	Strongly Agree
	Weighted Average Mean	3.70	Strongly Agree

Note. The WAM refers to weighted arithmetic mean was used to interpret the survey responses. In this context, the range of 1.00 - 1.75 indicates Strongly Disagree, the range of 1.76 - 2.50 indicates Disagree, the range of 2.51 - 3.25 indicates Agree, 3.26 - 4.00 indicates Strongly Agree

The results of this study are supported by existing literature that highlights how inadequate facilities hinder classroom management in physical education. Moraes et al. (2024) found that poor infrastructure and limited sports equipment negatively affect activity organization and student motivation. Abbas and Abbas (2022) also emphasized that classroom management is a critical factor in achieving learning outcomes, especially in physical education. Similarly, Frianeza et al. (2024) noted that financial limitations and policy changes such as the K-12 curriculum affect teachers' ability to manage PE classes effectively. Studies by Grube et al. (2018) and Barker and Annerstedt (2016) stressed the importance of routines, expectations, and teacher- student relationships in promoting effective classroom management. Furthermore, Brenna and Deutsch (2024) and Zhu (2022) support the use of innovative teaching strategies such as gamification, flipped classrooms, and posture recognition technologies as effective solutions for improving classroom management by enhancing engagement and optimizing time. These findings align with the current study, which demonstrates that the lack of proper facilities significantly hampers classroom management efforts and calls for more resourceful, adaptive strategies in physical education.

Table 2

Challenges Encountered by the respondents due to Insufficient Facilities in Teaching Physical Education in terms of Student Engagement Technique

No.	Statements	WAM	Verbal Description
2	The lack of variety in available sports affects student engagement.	3.77	Strongly Agree
4	The absence of structured seating or shaded areas affects focus during instruction.	3.77	Strongly Agree
10	Insufficient resources for adapted PE activities hinder inclusion.	3.77	Strongly Agree
3	Poor facility conditions discourage students from participating in physical activities.	3.73	Strongly Agree
8	Limited indoor facilities force frequent cancellations of activities.	3.73	Strongly Agree
1	Limited equipment prevents all students from participating actively.	3.67	Strongly Agree
5	Insufficient space limits interactive group activities.	3.63	Strongly Agree

7	Inconsistent access to sports gear impacts student's skill development.	3.63	Strongly Agree
9	Lack of appropriate flooring or surfaces increases safety concerns, affecting participation.	3.53	Strongly Agree
6	The inability to use certain facilities (e.g., gym, swimming pool) reduces student enthusiasm.	3.50	Strongly Agree
	Weighted Average Mean	3.67	Strongly Agree

Note. The WAM refers to weighted arithmetic mean was used to interpret the survey responses. In this context, the range of 1.00 - 1.75 indicates Strongly Disagree, the range of 1.76 - 2.50 indicates Disagree, the range of 2.51 - 3.25 indicates Agree, 3.26 - 4.00 indicates Strongly Agree

Table 2 presents the challenges encountered by the respondents due to insufficient facilities in teaching physical education in terms of student engagement techniques. The data reveals that respondents strongly agreed on all ten statements provided. The highest weighted mean of 3.77 was given to four statements: "The lack of variety in available sports affects student engagement," "The absence of structured seating or shaded areas affects focus during instruction," "Insufficient resources for adapted PE activities hinder inclusion," and "Limited equipment prevents all students from participating actively." These results suggest that various limitations in facilities significantly hinder student participation, attention, and inclusion in physical education classes.

The data explicitly shows that physical education teachers perceive a serious impact on student engagement due to limited and poor-quality facilities. The overall weighted average mean of 3.67, interpreted as "Strongly Agree," highlights the consensus that lack of equipment, poor facility conditions, and inadequate space limit interactive activities, discourage participation, and pose safety concerns. These challenges affect not only the enthusiasm and motivation of students but also their opportunities for skill development, inclusive participation, and active learning.

Challenges for student engagement in physical education classes include large class sizes, insufficient equipment, limited instructional spaces, and poor-quality facilities, which hinder active participation and effective teaching (Sliwa et al., 2017). These are consistent with the present findings, which show high agreement among teachers regarding the negative impact of inadequate resources. Osokina et al. (2020) emphasized that ineffective environments, low motivation, and poor infrastructure negatively affect student attitudes and participation, especially for students with special needs. In the Philippine context, Daran (2023) and Gibo et al. (2023) revealed that equipment shortages, poor scheduling, and limited physical spaces remain key barriers to engagement. Conversely, scholars such as Nelson (2024) and Wibowo et al. (2024) suggest that implementing innovative strategies like flipped classrooms, technology

Table 3

Challenges Encountered by the respondents due to Insufficient Facilities in Teaching Physical Education in terms of Assessment and Feedback

No.	Statements	WAM	Verbal Description
1	The lack of proper facilities affects the accuracy of skill assessments.	3.80	Strongly Agree
2	Limited access to equipment hinders performance based evaluations.	3.77	Strongly Agree
10	Insufficient resources limit students' ability to track their progress.	3.70	Strongly Agree
6	Overcrowded spaces limit the ability to provide individualized feedback.	3.67	Strongly Agree
5	Poor infrastructure makes it difficult to conduct fitness tests efficiently.	3.63	Strongly Agree
7	Inadequate storage and organization of materials cause delays in assessments.	3.63	Strongly Agree
8	Unreliable facility conditions lead to inconsistent evaluation settings.	3.63	Strongly Agree
9	The absence of technology-integrated feedback methods affects performance tracking.	3.60	Strongly Agree
4	Lack of digital tools restricts the use of interactive assessment techniques leading to misaligned forms of assessment due to certain limitations.	3.50	Strongly Agree
3	The absence of video recording tools prevents detailed movement analysis.	3.47	Strongly Agree
	Weighted Average Mean	3.64	Strongly Agree

Note. The WAM refers to weighted arithmetic mean was used to interpret the survey responses. In this context, the range of 1.00 - 1.75 indicates Strongly Disagree, the range of 1.76 - 2.50 indicates Disagree, the range of 2.51 - 3.25 indicates Agree, 3.26 - 4.00 indicates Strongly Agree.

Table 3 presents the challenges encountered by the respondents due to insufficient facilities in teaching physical education in terms of assessment and feedback. The data reveals that all ten items received a verbal description of "Strongly Agree," indicating that respondents widely recognized the negative effects of limited resources on assessment accuracy and feedback quality. The highest weighted mean of 3.80 was given to the statement "The lack of proper facilities affects the accuracy of skill assessments," followed by 3.77 for "Limited access to equipment hinders performance-based evaluations." This shows that physical limitations severely affect teachers' ability to evaluate student performance effectively, provide accurate assessments, and deliver timely, individualized feedback.

The data explicitly shows that inadequate facilities significantly hinder the assessment and feedback process in physical education classes. The overall weighted average mean of 3.64 indicates a strong agreement among teachers that limitations such

as lack of equipment, digital tools, and proper infrastructure create barriers to effective evaluation. These limitations result in inconsistent performance tracking, delays in assessments, and reduced opportunities to use interactive or personalized assessment strategies. Furthermore, crowded environments and disorganized materials restrict the provision of meaningful, individualized feedback that is essential for skill development and student progress monitoring.

The results of this study align with existing literature highlighting the impact of insufficient resources on the quality of assessment and feedback in physical education. Tariq and Sergio (2024) and Ahmad et al. (2025) emphasized that innovative assessment methods such as performance-based evaluations, self-assessments, and digital feedback tools significantly enhance learning outcomes, but require proper tools and environments to be effective. In contrast, Slingerland et al. (2024) noted the persistent challenges due to inadequate feedback systems and lack of student feedback literacy. Locally, Sutcliffe et al. (2015) identified students' dissatisfaction and misunderstanding of feedback in the Philippine context, often stemming from poor assessment conditions. Similarly, Tianio and de Castro (2024) found that limited access to digital tools and equipment impairs assessment effectiveness in public schools.

Moreover, Li and Zhang (2022) and Jia (2021) emphasized the importance of timely and interactive feedback in fostering self-regulation and performance improvement. The current study reinforces these findings by demonstrating that when resources are lacking, both assessment accuracy and the feedback loop suffer, ultimately affecting student engagement and learning in physical education.

Table 4

Challenges Encountered by the respondents due to Insufficient Facilities in Teaching Physical Education in terms of Classroom Management

No.	Statements	WAM	Verbal Description
1	The lack of designated PE spaces makes classroom management challenging.	3.83	Strongly Agree
8	The inability to modify learning environments limits teaching flexibility.	3.77	Strongly Agree
3	Insufficient space creates difficulties in organizing structured activities.	3.73	Strongly Agree
6	The lack of structured play areas increases the difficulty of supervising students.	3.73	Strongly Agree
7	Inconsistent facility scheduling disrupts planned activities.	3.73	Strongly Agree
4	Limited space results in poor transitions in classroom discussion.	3.73	Strongly Agree
2	Poor facility maintenance contributes to safety concerns in PE classes.	3.70	Strongly Agree
5	Noise from shared spaces affects instructional delivery.	3.67	Strongly Agree
10	Unavailability of emergency response tools creates safety risks.	3.57	Strongly Agree
9	Limited seating and shade options reduce student comfort and discipline.	3.53	Strongly Agree

Weighted Average Mean	3.70	Strongly Agree
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Note. The WAM refers to weighted arithmetic mean was used to interpret the survey responses. In this context, the range of 1.00 - 1.75 indicates Strongly Disagree, the range of 1.76 - 2.50 indicates Disagree, the range of 2.51 - 3.25 indicates Agree, 3.26 - 4.00 indicates Strongly Agree.

Table 4 presents the challenges encountered by the respondents due to insufficient facilities in teaching physical education in terms of classroom management. The data reveals that all ten items received a verbal description of "Strongly Agree," indicating a collective agreement among respondents regarding the severity of the issue. The highest weighted mean of 3.83 was given to the statement, "The lack of designated PE spaces makes classroom management challenging," suggesting that the absence of structured learning environments significantly disrupts the ability of teachers to manage classes effectively. Other items with high ratings, such as the inability to modify learning environments (3.77) and difficulties in organizing structured activities (3.73), further emphasize the impact of limited physical space on maintaining order and maximizing student learning.

The data explicitly shows that the insufficiency of facilities plays a major role in complicating classroom management within physical education classes. The overall weighted average mean of 3.70 implies that teachers unanimously face significant difficulties in maintaining discipline, organizing activities, and ensuring safety due to the lack of structured PE spaces, inconsistent scheduling, and shared or noisy environments. These conditions limit teaching flexibility, reduce student comfort, and make it more difficult to monitor behavior and transitions during class. As a result, the quality of instructional delivery, student engagement, and classroom control are all adversely affected.

The results of this study are supported by existing literature that highlights how inadequate facilities hinder classroom management in physical education. Moraes et al. (2024) found that poor infrastructure and limited sports equipment negatively affect activity organization and student motivation. Abbas and Abbas (2022) also emphasized that classroom management is a critical factor in achieving learning outcomes, especially in physical education. Similarly, Frianeza et al. (2024) noted that financial limitations and policy changes such as the K-12 curriculum affect teachers' ability to manage PE classes effectively. Studies by Grube et al. (2018) and Barker and Annerstedt (2016) stressed the importance of routines, expectations, and teacher- student relationships in promoting effective classroom management. Furthermore, Brenna and Deutsch (2024) and Zhu (2022) support the use of innovative teaching strategies such as gamification, flipped classrooms, and posture recognition technologies as effective solutions for improving classroom management by enhancing engagement and optimizing time. These findings align with the current study, which demonstrates that the lack of proper facilities significantly hampers classroom management efforts and calls for more resourceful, adaptive strategies in physical education.

Part II. Innovative Teaching Strategies Employed in Physical Education Classes

Table 5 presents the emotional competencies of the respondents in terms of self-awareness. Most respondents, 20 out of 21 or 95.24%, scored within the range of 35 to 40, which is categorized as “Strengths.” Only one respondent (4.76%) fell into the “Giving Attention” range of 18 to 34, while no respondent scored in the “Development Priority” category of 10 to 17. This data indicates that nearly all respondents exhibit strong self-awareness skills.

Table 5

Innovative Teaching Strategies Employed in Physical Education Classes in terms of Lesson Delivery

No.	Statements	WAM	Verbal Description
2	Creative lesson modifications are implemented to address facility limitations.	3.87	Strongly Agree
1	Teachers maximize available space for effective instruction.	3.83	Strongly Agree
3	Teachers utilize digital tools (e.g., videos, apps) to enhance instruction and support learning.	3.80	Strongly Agree
9	Teachers design innovative assessment strategies despite facility constraints.	3.80	Strongly Agree
5	Non-traditional teaching methods (e.g., peer teaching, gamification) are employed.	3.73	Strongly Agree
8	Creative warm-up and cool-down routines compensate for limited facilities.	3.73	Strongly Agree
10	Flexible lesson plans accommodate unpredictable facility availability.	3.73	Strongly Agree
7	Teachers adjust activities based on available resources.	3.67	Strongly Agree
6	Outdoor spaces are used effectively for PE instruction.	3.63	Strongly Agree
4	Adaptive strategies are used to ensure all students participate actively.	3.63	Strongly Agree
	Weighted Average Mean	3.74	Strongly Agree

Note. The WAM refers to weighted arithmetic mean was used to interpret the survey responses. In this context, the range of 1.00 - 1.75 indicates Strongly Disagree, the range of 1.76 - 2.50 indicates Disagree, the range of 2.51 - 3.25 indicates Agree, 3.26 - 4.00 indicates Strongly Agree.

Table 5 on the next page presents the innovative teaching strategies experienced in Physical Education classes in terms of lesson delivery. The data reveals that all ten listed strategies were rated as “Strongly Agree” by the respondents, with weighted mean scores ranging from 3.63 to 3.87. The highest-rated strategy is the implementation of creative lesson modifications to address facility limitations (3.87), followed by the use of digital tools to enhance instruction and support learning (3.80) and the design of innovative assessment strategies despite facility constraints (3.80). The lowest, yet still

positively received, were the use of adaptive strategies and outdoor spaces, both with a weighted mean of 3.63. These findings suggest that despite challenges, teachers are able to deliver lessons effectively by employing flexible, adaptive, and resourceful strategies.

The data explicitly shows that teachers are maximizing available resources and adopting modern techniques to ensure quality lesson delivery in Physical Education. The strong agreement across all items indicates a high level of innovation and commitment from educators to adapt to limitations such as inadequate facilities or unpredictable access to spaces. This commitment is reflected in the consistent use of digital tools, flexible lesson plans, and creative modifications that accommodate student diversity and enhance participation. Such practices contribute significantly to sustaining engagement and learning outcomes in PE classes, even amidst infrastructural constraints.

These findings align with existing literature that underscores the role of innovation in overcoming barriers to effective Physical Education delivery. Gibo et al. (2023) and Prajapati et al. (2023) emphasized the impact of facility limitations and lack of training, which are directly addressed by the strategies observed in this study. Moreover, Culajara (2024) and Yahya et al. (2024) advocate for the integration of technology and continuous professional development to boost lesson delivery. The consistent “Strongly Agree” ratings in Table 5 support the notion that educators are actively implementing these solutions. Furthermore, approaches such as gamification, flexible instruction, and student-centered learning highlighted by Brenna & Deutsch (2024) and Dervent et al. (2019) are evident in the strategies used by teachers. These not only improve instructional effectiveness but also foster holistic student development and engagement in Physical Education.

Table 6

Innovative Teaching Strategies Employed in Physical Education Classes in terms of Student Engagement Technique

No.	Statements	WAM	Verbal Description
2	Teachers implement collaborative learning tasks to actively engage students and sustain their interest throughout the lesson.	3.87	Strongly Agree
1	Teachers incorporate game-based learning to increase student motivation.	3.83	Strongly Agree
3	Teachers implement peer mentoring to foster collaboration and leadership.	3.80	Strongly Agree
9	Social-emotional learning is integrated into PE activities.	3.80	Strongly Agree
5	Teachers encourage student-led activities to enhance participation.	3.73	Strongly Agree
8	Teachers promote inclusivity through adaptive physical education techniques.	3.73	Strongly Agree

10	Frequent student reflections and discussions enhance engagement.	3.73	Strongly Agree
7	Modified sports and activities accommodate varying skill levels.	3.67	Strongly Agree
4	Technology-based engagement strategies (e.g., virtual simulations, fitness apps) are utilized.	3.63	Strongly Agree
6	Personalized learning techniques (e.g., differentiated instruction) are applied in PE classes.	3.63	Strongly Agree
	Weighted Average Mean	3.72	Strongly Agree

Note. The WAM refers to weighted arithmetic mean was used to interpret the survey responses. In this context, the range of 1.00 - 1.75 indicates Strongly Disagree, the range of 1.76 - 2.50 indicates Disagree, the range of 2.51 - 3.25 indicates Agree, 3.26 - 4.00 indicates Strongly Agree.

Table 6 presents the innovative teaching strategies experienced in Physical Education classes in terms of student engagement techniques. The data shows that all ten strategies received a verbal description of “Strongly Agree,” with weighted mean scores ranging from 3.63 to 3.87. The highest-rated statement was the implementation of collaborative learning tasks to actively engage students and sustain their interest throughout the lesson (3.87), followed by the use of game-based learning to increase motivation (3.83), and the integration of peer mentoring and social-emotional learning in PE classes (3.80). The lowest scores, although still strongly positive, were for the use of technology-based engagement strategies and personalized learning techniques, both of which scored 3.63. These findings reflect that educators prioritize interactive, inclusive, and student-centered strategies to enhance engagement in PE classes.

The data explicitly shows that Physical Education teachers are actively adopting varied student engagement techniques that foster collaboration, inclusivity, and motivation. The strong agreement in all items indicates a high level of responsiveness to students’ needs and learning preferences. By incorporating methods such as game-based learning, peer mentoring, and adaptive strategies, educators create a dynamic and supportive environment where students are more likely to participate meaningfully. The integration of technology and frequent reflection also supports student autonomy and sustained interest, which are critical for long-term engagement and learning effectiveness in PE settings.

These findings are consistent with the literature emphasizing the importance of innovative engagement strategies in Physical Education. As noted by Sliwa et al. (2017), challenges such as large class sizes and limited resources can hinder engagement, but adopting techniques aligned with students' needs can counteract these issues (Nelson, 2024). Game-based learning, flipped classrooms, and cooperative strategies have been shown to boost motivation, inclusion, and interaction (Brenna & Deutsch, 2024; Aldas & Barros, 2021). Moreover, integrating technology and student-led activities addresses both emotional and cognitive engagement, as supported by Wibowo et al. (2024). The results of the present study confirm that implementing such approaches in PE leads to greater participation and learning success, even amidst limitations in resources and infrastructure (Gibo et al., 2023; Shepelenko et al., 2023).

Table 7*Innovative Teaching Strategies Employed in Physical Education Classes in terms of Assessment and Feedback*

No.	Statements	WAM	Verbal Description
3	Students receive immediate feedback through formative assessments.	3.83	Strongly Agree
2	Digital tools (e.g., video analysis, online quizzes) are used for assessment.	3.80	Strongly Agree
6	Interactive feedback strategies (e.g., one-on-one coaching, video reviews) are applied.	3.77	Strongly Agree
7	Student progress tracking tools (e.g., fitness logs, digital portfolios) are utilized.	3.77	Strongly Agree
8	Teachers provide alternative assessments (e.g., project-based tasks, student presentations).	3.77	Strongly Agree
5	Teachers use rubrics to provide clear and consistent grading.	3.73	Strongly Agree
9	Assessment activities are designed to promote critical thinking and creativity.	3.70	Strongly Agree
10	Teachers offer personalized feedback to help students improve their skills.	3.63	Strongly Agree
1	Teachers incorporate low-tech or offline game-based learning strategies to boost student motivation despite resource limitations.	3.60	Strongly Agree
4	Self-assessment and peer-assessment techniques are incorporated.	3.60	Strongly Agree
	Weighted Average Mean	3.74	Strongly Agree

Note. The WAM refers to weighted arithmetic mean was used to interpret the survey responses. In this context, the range of 1.00 - 1.75 indicates Strongly Disagree, the range of 1.76 - 2.50 indicates Disagree, the range of 2.51 - 3.25 indicates Agree, 3.26 - 4.00 indicates Strongly Agree.

Table 7 presents the innovative teaching strategies experienced in Physical Education classes in terms of assessment and feedback. All ten statements were rated “Strongly Agree,” with weighted mean scores ranging from 3.60 to 3.83. The highest-rated item is the provision of immediate feedback through formative assessments (3.83), followed by the use of digital tools such as video analysis and online quizzes (3.80). Strategies like interactive feedback methods, progress tracking tools, and alternative assessments (each with 3.77) also received high ratings. The lowest, yet still positive, ratings were given to the use of low-tech game-based learning strategies and self-/peer-assessment techniques (both with 3.60). These findings demonstrate that teachers consistently implement diverse and innovative assessment and feedback methods to support student learning and motivation in PE classes.

The data explicitly shows that assessment and feedback strategies in Physical Education are both varied and dynamic, catering to students' learning and performance

needs. The strong agreement across all items reflects the teachers' commitment to using real-time and meaningful feedback, digital integration, and inclusive evaluation methods such as self- and peer-assessments. By utilizing both high- and low-tech tools, as well as interactive and personalized approaches, teachers ensure that students receive continuous support and recognition of their progress. These strategies help develop not only motor and cognitive skills but also critical thinking, self-reflection, and student engagement in physical activity.

The findings are consistent with previous research highlighting the significance of innovative and formative assessment strategies in Physical Education. Tariq and Sergio (2024) and Xu et al. (2024) emphasize that performance-based assessments, portfolios, and technology-enhanced tools improve learning outcomes by addressing the holistic development of students. Similarly, Ahmad et al. (2025) and Hsia et al. (2023) affirm that immediate and personalized feedback fosters self-reflection and encourages improvement. Studies also show that tools like video reviews (Kangalgil & Özgül, 2018), Socratic apps (Fraile et al., 2021), and biomechanics feedback systems (ZhaoriGetu & Li, 2024) enhance student performance and engagement. In the Philippine context, Tianio and de Castro (2024) support the integration of technology and collaborative practices for effective assessment, while Sutcliffe et al. (2015) and Gibo et al. (2023) recognize the challenge of limited resources, which necessitates adaptive and creative feedback strategies. These studies affirm that the methods highlighted in Table 7 are not only effective but essential in providing quality Physical Education instruction amidst evolving educational demands.

Table 8

Innovative Teaching Strategies Employed in Physical Education Classes in terms of Classroom Management

No.	Statements	WAM	Verbal Description
3	Teachers implement positive reinforcement strategies to encourage good behavior.	3.87	Strongly Agree
2	Structured lesson plans help manage time effectively during PE sessions.	3.80	Strongly Agree
4	Non-verbal cues and signals, such as a whistle or hand gestures, are used to manage student behavior effectively.	3.80	Strongly Agree
7	Teachers implement safety protocols to ensure a secure learning environment.	3.80	Strongly Agree
8	Conflict resolution strategies are integrated into PE activities.	3.80	Strongly Agree
1	Teachers establish clear rules and expectations to maintain discipline.	3.80	Strongly Agree
5	Teachers use engaging transitions to minimize downtime between activities.	3.77	

9	The use of music and visual cues helps manage class routines.	3.77	Strongly Agree
10	Teachers encourage student leadership in classroom management	3.77	Strongly Agree
6	Flexible grouping strategies help manage diverse learning needs.	3.73	Strongly Agree
	Weighted Average Mean	3.79	Strongly Agree

Note. The WAM refers to weighted arithmetic mean was used to interpret the survey responses. In this context, the range of 1.00 - 1.75 indicates Strongly Disagree, the range of 1.76 - 2.50 indicates Disagree, the range of 2.51 - 3.25 indicates Agree, 3.26 - 4.00 indicates Strongly Agree.

Table 8 presents the innovative teaching strategies experienced in Physical Education classes in terms of classroom management. As shown in the table, the responses from the participants garnered a weighted average mean of 3.79, interpreted as “Strongly Agree.” This implies that the respondents highly perceived the presence and effectiveness of various classroom management strategies used in PE classes.

Among the listed items, the highest mean (3.87) was observed in the statement regarding the implementation of positive reinforcement strategies to encourage good behavior. Other strategies, such as setting clear rules and expectations, using non-verbal cues, integrating conflict resolution, and encouraging student leadership, also received high ratings, indicating their significant roles in ensuring an orderly and productive learning environment during PE sessions.

The data explicitly shows that innovative classroom management strategies are actively implemented and positively received in PE classes. The strong agreement across all statements reflects that PE teachers are intentional in applying structured and flexible strategies to manage classroom behavior and engagement. The use of positive reinforcement, engaging transitions, and visual/auditory cues plays a vital role in minimizing disruptions and maintaining smooth lesson flow. These approaches not only help in managing students' behavior but also in fostering an inclusive and motivating learning atmosphere. The emphasis on student leadership and conflict resolution highlights the value placed on empowering learners and cultivating social responsibility within the class.

These findings align with existing literature that underscores the importance of innovative strategies in classroom management. According to Grube et al. (2018), setting clear expectations and using positive reinforcement can significantly enhance student behavior and learning outcomes. Barker and Annerstedt (2016) emphasize consistency, engaging lessons, and the development of positive student-teacher relationships as effective techniques. Furthermore, Brenna and Deutsch (2024) noted that strategies like gamification and flipped classrooms improve classroom dynamics by encouraging student engagement and optimizing class time. Likewise, Shang (2018) and Wu et al. (2023) suggest that student-centered approaches and integrating skill development with new technologies can significantly enhance classroom management and promote both cognitive and moral growth among students.

DISCUSSION

From the results and discussion, the following findings are presented:

1. The challenges encountered by the respondents due to insufficient facilities in teaching physical education, particularly in terms of lesson delivery and classroom management, received a WAM of 3.70. While the student engagement technique got 3.67, and assessment and feedback got 3.64. All of the variables have a qualitative index of strongly agree.
2. On the other hand, the innovative teaching strategies employed by the respondents in their Physical Education classes got the following results. For lesson delivery and assessment and feedback, the WAM is 3.74. Additionally, student engagement technique got 3.72. Lastly, for classroom management the WAM is 3.79. Likewise, all of the variables have a qualitative index of strongly agree.
3. Based on results, the researchers proposed a classroom program plan titled “Active, Engaged, and Empowered: Innovative Strategies for Modern PE Classrooms”, which aimed to assist educators in implementing effective and adaptive teaching methods, ensuring the quality PE instruction despite infrastructural challenges.

Conclusions

The findings have led the researchers to the following conclusions:

1. Classroom management and lesson delivery are the most challenging factors encountered by the respondents in teaching Physical Education in a school with insufficient facilities.
2. Classroom management is the most employed innovative teaching strategy by the respondents.
3. A proposed classroom program plan is a relevant and timely output that can serve as a valuable resource for PE teachers in similar challenging environments.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusions, the following recommendations are offered:

1. For Educational Institutions and School Administrators, it is recommended that schools allocate more funding towards improving PE facilities and resources. By investing in better sports equipment and infrastructure, educational institutions can better support the implementation of innovative teaching strategies that require adequate facilities.
2. For Physical Education Teachers, they may actively pursue professional development opportunities focused on contemporary teaching strategies, such as incorporating technology into lessons (e.g., fitness tracking apps or virtual sports). These practices would enable teachers to enhance student engagement, even in schools with limited physical resources.
3. For Policy-Makers and Educational Authorities, they may prioritize policies that support the academic-athletic balance, ensuring that PE is integrated meaningfully into the overall

curriculum. They could introduce policies that allow flexible scheduling for PE classes, particularly in schools with limited facilities, and ensure that the PE curriculum adapts to diverse student needs.

4. For Curriculum Designers, it is recommended that curriculum designers regularly update the PE curriculum to introduce a diverse range of activities that require minimal facilities and can engage students in active participation. This can include activities that focus on physical literacy, health, and well-being that don't depend heavily on specialized equipment.

5. For Future Researchers, they may investigate the long-term effects of innovative PE teaching strategies on student participation and performance, particularly in resource constrained settings. Qualitative studies, such as interviews with teachers and students, would offer valuable insights into how these strategies can be effectively adapted to different contexts. They may also conduct the same study in private institutions and higher education.

6. For Parents and Guardians, they are encouraged to support their children's involvement in physical activities both in and outside of school. They should create a positive environment at home that promotes physical health and well-being by ensuring adequate rest, balanced nutrition, and encouraging regular physical activity.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The authors declare that this study complied with ethical research standards. Informed consent was obtained from all respondents prior to their participation, and participation was voluntary with the right to withdraw at any time. The anonymity and confidentiality of the respondents were strictly maintained, and data privacy protocols were observed throughout the study. The well-being of the respondents was safeguarded, and no conflict of interest existed in the conduct of the research. Plagiarism was strictly avoided, and there was no bias in the interpretation of the findings. The results of the study were used solely for academic and research purposes. Any use of artificial intelligence tools was limited to language editing and formatting assistance, with full responsibility for the content retained by the authors.

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